

DYNAMIC IN-PLANE DAMAGE AND FAILURE OF ANGLE-INTERLOCK WOVEN COMPOSITE MATERIAL

Zhongxiang Pan¹, Bohong Gu², Baozhong Sun² and Jie Xiong¹

¹ College of Materials & Textiles, Zhejiang Sci-Tech University, Hangzhou, 310018, China, panzx@zstu.edu.cn, jxiong@zstu.edu.cn

² College of Textiles, Donghua University, Shanghai, 201620, China, gubh@dhu.edu.cn, sunbz@dhu.edu.cn

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ABSTRACT

Interlaminar strength is important for the reliability of a multilayer material. Angle-interlock woven composites may have different in-plane mechanical behaviors along their warp and weft directions. This work is aimed to investigate the dynamic in-plane damage and failure progress of an angle-interlock woven composite by high-speed imaging during impact compression. Real-time images were listed frame by frame and located in stress-strain curves. It is found that post-yield response includes a sharp decrease stage and a steady decrease stage in stress. The sharp decrease in stress revealed a fast and drastic change from cracking accumulation quickly to explosive damage. The steady decrease in stress indicated a progress by the evolution of dynamic damage and failure. For the warp-direction impact compression, dispersive shear cracks were accumulated along the warp/matrix interfaces and propagated through the several layers of the composite. Specimens were fractured by shear-delamination cracks along the paths of warp yarns due to the lack of binding effect of straight weft yarns. For the weft-direction impact compression, interlaminar cracks were developed at weft/matrix interfaces and made openings among different layers of weft yarns. But the inter-locked warp yarns protected the composite from being thoroughly split under the trend of delamination.

1 INTRODUCTION

Angle-interlock woven composites are self-enhanced because multi-layer wefts can be angle-locked by the interlacing warps. Such structure gives the angle-interlock woven composites good through-thickness mechanical properties [1]. Composite components are likely to experience shock and impact loadings during usage in aerospace, military, transportation, sports and civil engineering applications. Researchers in the last three years have made progress in the impact dynamics of textile structural composites. For examples, Gu et al [2], Wan et al [3], Zhou et al [4], Pan et al [5, 6] and Li et al [7] studied the ballistic perforation, impact compressive properties, transverse impact behaviors, thermal mechanical coupling responses and punch shear behaviors of the 3-D braided composites respectively. Fang et al [8], Sun et al [9] and Pan et al [10] studied the impact compressive behaviors, impact tensile behaviors and temperature-influenced impact damage of the biaxial warp-knitted composites respectively. Luan et al [11] and Behera et al [12] studied the energy absorption under ballistic penetration and the impact resistance of angle-interlock woven composites respectively.

However, few studies [13, 14] have given the high-speed damages of textile structural composites under impact loadings. Shear-resistance or delamination-resistance is quite important for the reliability of the Interlaminar strength of a composite material. Experimentally, there still exists many unbeknown details on the in-plane failure process of angle-interlock woven composites during high-speed deformation. Aided by the high-speed imaging technique, the objectives for this study are to investigate the progressive failure of angle-interlock woven composites by capturing the real-time images during high-strain rate compression. Dynamic failures along the warp and weft directions of the angle-interlock woven composite specimens were recorded with their stress-strain curves. It is envisaged that this work will provide insights to aid the design of 3-D woven composites under high-speed applications.

2 MATERIALS

Table 1 provides the basic specification of the angle-interlock woven composites. Figure 1 shows the angle-interlock woven perform structure and its composite specimen. The interlacing warps went through layers of straight wefts and twined them to increase the inter-layer mechanical properties. After the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) and thermal curing process, specimens of the angle-interlock woven composites were prepared for impact tests.

Table 1 Basic specification of the angle-interlock woven composite

	Warp	Weft
Weaving density	80 ends /10 cm	38 ends / 10 cm
Yarn linear density	800 tex	1600 tex
Layers in fabric	7	
Fiber volume fraction	43.2 %	

Figure 1 The angle-interlock fabric, woven structure and its composite specimen

3 DYNAMIC EXPERIMENTS

The split Hopkinson bar (SHPB) testing technique [15, 16] provided an important approach to obtain the dynamic response of materials under high strain rates usually from 10^2 to 10^4 s^{-1} . It is illustrated in Figure 2. The bars were made of steel with the density $\rho=7.8$ g/cm^3 and Young's modulus $E=191.9$ GPa. Length of the striker bar, incident bar and transmission bar is 500 mm, 1800 mm and 1200 mm, respectively. All the bars had the same diameter of 12.7 mm.

Figure 2 The split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) system and stress wave propagation, transmission and reflection along bars

When high pressure nitrogen gas is released from a chamber, it propels the striker through a barrel to impact the incident bar. This generates an elastic stress wave ($C_0 = \sqrt{E/\rho} = 4947$ m/s) with a length equal to twice that of the striker. When the input bar signal is detected by the oscilloscope, the flash is activated to illuminate the specimen and image capture by the high-speed camera begins. When the elastic compressive wave reaches the specimen-incident bar interface, part of it reflects back as an elastic tensile wave into the incident bar, while the rest of the compressive wave transmits through specimen into the transmission bar. To measure the incident, reflected and transmitted pulses, strain gauges are mounted on the incident and transmission bars. The strain rate ($\dot{\varepsilon}$), strain (ε), and stress (σ) in the specimen are given by:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}(t) = \frac{2C_0}{L_s} [\varepsilon_i(t) - \varepsilon_t(t)] \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{2C_0}{L_s} \int_0^t [\varepsilon_i(t) - \varepsilon_t(t)] dt \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma(t) = E \frac{A_b}{A_s} \varepsilon_i(t) \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon_i(t)$ and $\varepsilon_t(t)$ are respectively, the strain signals associated with the incident and transmitted pulses, L_s is the specimen length, and A_b and A_s are the respective cross-sectional areas of the incident/transmission bars and specimen. Typical signals of the angle-interlock woven composites are shown in Figure 3. The stress-strain curves under impact compression can be calculated using the Equation(1)-(3).

Figure 3 Typical signals of the warp-direction and weft-direction impact compression captured from the SHPB system

For the high-speed camera, the visual area and its resolution would decrease with the increase of the framing rate. The maximum framing rate of the camera was 500,000 Hz. After comprehensive consideration, the framing rate used was 100,000 Hz. The duration of the incident wave pulse was 200 μ s. In other words, there were 20 frames captured by the high-speed imaging system during once impact. And the size of each captured picture was 192*128 pixels. This ensured enough dynamic images as well as good visual area and resolution to demonstrate progressive details at macro-scale.

Figure 4 The (a) warp-direction and (b) weft-direction loading of the angle-interlock woven composite specimens for the SHPB tests

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Dynamic stress-strain behavior

Figure 5 illustrates the stress-strain behavior of the angle-interlock woven composite specimens subjected to impact loading along the warp and weft direction. Post-yield responses of all stress-strain curves show the sharp decrease stage and steady decrease stage in stress. The two stages indicates different dynamic damage or failure progress which could be analyzed with the help of high-speed images.

From Figure 6, it is found that the weft-direction performances (including dynamic compressive modulus and peak strength) were better than the warp-direction ones. It is caused by the structural difference of angle-interlock woven reinforcement along the warp and weft direction. Since all of the weft yarns were in-plane arranged straightly, such non-crimp yarns benefit the mechanical properties along the weft direction by providing enough stiffness and strength.

Figure 5 The (a) warp-direction and (c) weft-direction stress-strain behavior of the angle-interlock woven composite specimens

Figure 6 The dynamic stiffness and strength of the angle-interlock woven composite specimens along the warp and weft directions

4.2 Warp-direction dynamic damage and failure

During the warp-direction impact compression, all the specimens experienced catastrophic failure progress along the warp direction. For 526/s in Figure 7, from 40 μ s to about 100 μ s, the post-yield stress dropped quickly. The sharp decrease stage accomplished within 60 μ s, during which the material experienced shear crack accumulation and delamination failure progress. For 2177/s in Figure 8, from

40 μ s to about 80 μ s, the sharp decrease stage accomplished shear crack accumulation and delamination failure progress within 40 μ s. The explosive shear-delamination cracks along warp direction led to catastrophic failures during the steady decrease stage from 80 to 180 μ s.

Figure 7 Warp-direction impact compression of angle-interlock woven composite specimen forming explosive shear-delamination failure at 526/s

Figure 8 Warp-direction impact compression of angle-interlock woven composite specimen forming explosive shear-delamination failure at 2177/s

Figure 9 and 10 illustrate the critical damage and failure progress selected during the warp-direction compression at 526/s and 2177/s, respectively. It is found that dispersive shear cracks were accumulated along the warp/matrix interfaces and propagated through the several layers of the composite. Since there was no interlacing effect by straight weft yarns, these shear cracks finally resulted in explosive shear-delamination failure of the composite.

The angle-interlocked woven composite material used in this study had a “layer-to-layer” characteristic along its warp-direction paths. Therefore, in case of dynamic in-plane failures, any possible impact loadings along the warp direction of the material should be paid much more attentions for shock-proof design.

Figure 9 Critical damage and failure progress during the warp-direction compression at 526/s

Figure 10 Critical damage and failure progress during the warp-direction compression at 2177/s

4.3 Weft-direction dynamic damage

For the weft-direction impact compression of the angle-interlock woven composite specimen at 1120/s in Figure 11, from about 50 μ s to 100 μ s, the post-yield stress dropped quickly. The sharp decrease stage accomplished within 50 μ s, during which the material experienced interlaminar cracks accumulation and delamination progress. While the steady decrease stage, from 120 to 180 μ s, reveals a progressive damaged morphologies. Similar phenomenon was also observed for the composite specimen at 1729/s in Figure 12.

During the weft-direction impact compression, as illustrated in Figure 13 and 14, the interlaminar cracks were developed at weft/matrix interfaces in specimens. These interlaminar cracks made openings which could result in Mode-I fracture among different layers of weft yarns. That is why the left end of the specimens were expanded. And the in-plane openings propagated along the weft/matrix interfaces from the left end to the right end.

However, from Figure 11(10) and 12(10), it is found that the right end of specimens was not split by the progressive interlaminar cracks. It indicates that the trend of explosive delamination were finally stopped. Because the multi-layer binding effect of the angle-interlocked warps played a positive role in repressing the propagation of the in-plane opening cracks effectively.

Figure 11 Weft-direction impact compression of angle-interlock woven composite specimen forming explosive interlaminar damages at 1120/s

Figure 12 Weft-direction impact compression of angle-interlock woven composite specimen forming explosive interlaminar damages at 1729/s

Figure 13 Critical damage progress during the weft-direction compression at 1120/s

Figure 14 Critical damage progress during the weft-direction compression at 1729/s

5 CONCLUSION

Stress-strain curves with their real-time images were helpful to analyze the progress of high-strain rate compression. The post-yield response of the angle-interlock woven composite included a sharp decrease stage and a steady decrease stage in stress. The sharp decrease in stress revealed a fast and drastic change from cracking accumulation quickly to explosive damage. The steady decrease in stress indicated a progress by the evolution of explosive damage and failure.

For the warp-direction impact compression, dispersive shear cracks were accumulated along the warp/matrix interfaces and propagated through the several layers of the composite. Since there was no interlacing effect by straight weft yarns, these shear cracks finally resulted in explosive shear-delamination failure of the composite.

For the weft-direction impact compression, interlaminar cracks were developed at weft/matrix interfaces and made openings which could lead to Mode-I fractures among different layers of weft yarns. But the trend of explosive delamination were finally stopped due to the multi-layer binding effect of the angle-interlocked warps in repressing the propagation of the in-plane opening cracks.

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